

"GREEN" STANDARDS - SUSTAINABLE HOUSING AS THE MAIN FACTOR OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article examines the construction of buildings and structures in the republic based on international standards of "green" construction, in particular, trends in the development of housing construction and an analysis of the provision of housing to the population in recent years, the main directions of development of sustainable housing construction, and also highlights important aspects of the development of sustainable housing construction as a result of the introduction of a system of "green" standards in the design, construction and operation of residential buildings.*

Keywords: *"green" standards, "green" housing construction, "green" certification systems, national economic driver, building culture, housing culture, local resources, sustainable housing construction, ecological housing, environmentally friendly materials, smart home, innovative technologies, limited resources, passive heating and cooling methods.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the construction industry in our republic is becoming a driver of the national economy. Construction of modern buildings and structures, in particular modern housing construction, including the international business center "Tashkent City", the residential complex "Almazor Business City", the multi-profile complex "Piramit Tower" and many others. Houses are not only a landmark of our cities, but once again show that our country is joining the ranks of developing countries of the world scale. Of course, aspects related to the unique nationality and culture of the industry are of great importance in the foundation of the above-mentioned high-rise buildings.

According to foreign countries, today almost half of the world's population lives in cities, and forecasts show that by 2030 about 75 percent of the population will become city dwellers. Consequently, the need for housing will increase, and at the same time the impact on the environment will increase [4].

Along with modern industrial and technical development, construction has received wider development and has become more rational. New building materials and technologies have begun to appear. Buildings and structures have become taller, larger and more functional. In particular, sustainable housing construction is rapidly developing, new concepts and approaches are emerging, such as the use of environmentally friendly materials. Housing construction has become more innovative and sustainable and has become primarily focused on the needs of the population.

Sustainable housing is understood as housing that is designed and built with maximum emphasis on environmental, social and economic sustainability as environmentally friendly or "green" housing.

It should be noted that the development of sustainable housing construction is based on certain principles that allow for the creation of high-quality and durable "green" structures. It

covers all stages of the process of constructing residential buildings, that is, the life cycle from the design of buildings to the end of their operation.

Main part. The developed countries have adopted "green" certification systems that include a set of criteria and requirements for assessing environmentally friendly real estate objects in order to create green buildings and sustainable territories. These systems, in turn, stimulate the active development of an innovative segment of the construction market - the "green" housing construction market. At the same time, in the reproduction of this type of "green" objects by producers, end consumers and other relevant participants in the green construction market and business partners, as well as state support at all stages of the life cycle of objects, a system of appropriate measures is needed.

In housing construction, projects are constantly being improved and adapted to local conditions, and also take into account all the needs associated with the economic, social and climatic conditions of a particular area, using local resources as efficiently as possible.

Each society has its own traditions of housing construction, as a result of which we can talk about architecture that reflects specific construction methods and lifestyle. However, local construction culture does not remain unchanged. This goes hand in hand with the development of society. This is due to the development of political, economic, socio-humanitarian, spiritual-educational and cultural ties between countries at different levels, as well as the emergence of new: knowledge and skills, construction technologies, technologies and methods, building materials, objects and can be explained by the emergence of structures.

Together with the above facts, the construction industry has a huge potential for sustainable development, which is described by the term "green" construction. This, in turn, presupposes the use of resource-efficient and environmentally responsible approaches that reduce the negative impact on the environment at all stages of the life cycle of construction projects, as well as more rational use of material and energy resources.

According to the United Nations' Environment Programme (UNEP), the use of raw materials is expected to double by 2060, further increasing the burden on the environment. In addition, the production of building materials such as cement, steel and concrete is a major source of greenhouse gases and emissions[4].

The issue of "green" standards has been discussed in the international community since the end of the last century. In some developed countries, the first "green" building standards were developed and corresponding government policies emerged.

It should be noted that the BREEM (BRE Environmental Assessment Method) rating for "green" buildings was developed in the UK, and the LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) eco-certification system was developed in the USA. In early 2000, the German Sustainable Building Council (DGNB) developed new standards that analyze the environmental sustainability of a building in the future, taking into account the functionality of the building in the next 50 years. In 2022, as part of the development of the national real estate appraisal system, two new "green" construction standards were developed in the Russian Federation: GOST R, designed to assess apartment buildings, and CLEVERS for commercial and non-commercial real estate objects and they began to operate simultaneously [4].

The goal of the BREEM, LEED and DGNB rating systems is the same - saving resources and reducing the negative impact of the created artificial human habitat on the environment and their own health. That is why most "green" standards pay special attention to socio-economic

factors and energy efficiency indicators. At the beginning of the new millennium, the World Green Building Council (WorldGBC) was created - an intergovernmental network organization uniting similar councils around the world. Every year, this Council, headquartered in Canada, holds the World Green Building Congress [7].

The standards that are successfully operating today can be adapted to the legal requirements of almost any country. Thus, many international green building standards have been adapted in many other countries. It should be noted that the Republic has in effect SHNK 2.07.05-19 - "Green construction. Residential and public buildings. The rating system for assessing the sustainability of the living environment has been approved" [5], this document meets the needs of today's generation for a comfortable living environment and human activity that meets the goals of fulfilling state functions through the use of residential buildings and public facilities without reducing the level of opportunities determined by the rating system for assessing the sustainability of the environment. The requirements of this rating system are to reduce energy consumption, use non-traditional, renewable and secondary energy resources, rational use of water, in the process of building construction and use aimed at reducing the harmful impact on the environment.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to housing construction in our country. It should be noted that during this period, 326 thousand new houses were built and commissioned in the Republic, the level of provision per capita increased by 18 percent, which is a practical expression of reforms aimed at glorifying human dignity on the path to building new Uzbekistan, as well as providing housing to the population. [6].

A total of 81,882.5 thousand square meters of housing was commissioned, of which 53,337.3 thousand square meters - in rural areas, 28,545.2 thousand square meters - in cities. Commissioning of residential buildings increased from 11,456.4 thousand square meters in 2017 to 14,612.6 thousand square meters in 2022. or by 27.5% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of housing commissioning in urban and rural areas of the republic in 2017-2022 (thousand square meters) [8]

According to the statistical department, as of January 1, 2023, the indicator of housing provision to the population in our republic averages 18.5 square meters of total living space per

inhabitant. This indicator increased by 0.3 square meters compared to the corresponding period of 2021 (Fig. 2).

Provision of housing to the population and its availability (housing availability) is an important factor in the socio-economic development of our country. This directly affects the standard of living of the population of the republic and is reflected in the demographic situation, and also affects the economic culture of the population, because a large amount of money is required to purchase housing.

In Uzbekistan, serious attention is paid to issues of housing construction and its operation. The fact is that providing the population with housing is not only a major social problem, but also one of the mandatory attributes that determine and ensure a normal human life.

The above allows us to emphasize that today the republic has a unique demographic situation, which has a significant impact on increasing the social significance of providing the population with housing in the course of large-scale reforms.

Figure 2. The dynamics of the housing provision indicator for the population of the republic In 2017-2022 (on average per 1 person, sq.m.) [9]

Sustainable development of local housing construction is often determined by the requirement to take into account and respect the traditions established in society. Sustainable development of housing construction is an important component of the development of society. It covers a wide range of knowledge, skills and values associated with the process of construction and operation of residential buildings. From this point of view, important issues are the main aspects of housing and construction culture, its history, principles, role in society, impact on the environment, as well as its problems and development prospects.

In housing construction, it is important to take into account not only the functionality and safety of the facility, but also its harmony with the environment. From this point of view, the use of modern construction technologies and materials in housing construction allows you to build environmentally friendly, energy- and resource-saving facilities. The use of such solutions leads not only to a negative impact on the environment, but also to a significant reduction in operating costs.

Sustainable development of housing construction is crucial for the development of industries and sectors of country's economy. That is why, based on innovative approaches, high-quality, resource- and energy-saving new residential buildings are built, economic efficiency and

a further increase in the standard of living of the population are achieved. The main goal in the construction of residential buildings is to ensure high quality of construction and installation works, compliance with norms and standards, and increase the efficiency of construction activities. Conclusions and suggestions. In addition to the large-scale reforms and changes in legislation currently being implemented in the republic, a number of international organizations fully support the transition of the economy of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030.

On January 29 of this year, President Sh. Mirziyoyev at a videoconference meeting [3] held in connection with the discussion of priority tasks in the areas of housing and communal services, construction, transport and ecology, in order to create decent conditions for the population and ensure the quality of life of the population, the introduction of modern standards in the field and quality assurance, a new organization of all processes from the design to the commissioning of the facility; from January 1, 2025, the resource method of preparation, construction and acceptance of all design and estimate documentation will be abandoned, while special attention was paid to such important tasks as the transition to the method, digitalization of the facility delivery process, coordination of documents in the national information system "Transparent Construction". At the same time, Presidential Decree PD-70 of April 30, 2024 "On additional measures to improve the mechanisms for providing mortgage loans in 2024 and improving the housing conditions of the population" [1] based on market principles within the framework of the program for providing the population with housing through mortgage lending, many tasks have been set, in particular, the introduction of "green" housing standards in the processes of multi-storey housing construction.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the Decree of the President PD-5577 of November 14, 2018 "On additional measures to improve state regulation of the construction industry" [2] should be noted. Separately, it can be noted that from January 1, 2018 Since 2020, the republic has established mandatory requirements for equipping housing construction projects with energy-efficient and energy-saving equipment at the stage of design and survey and construction and installation works.

At the same time, as a result of the introduction of a system of "green" standards in the processes of design, construction and operation of housing in cities and villages throughout the republic, it is necessary to pay attention to the following important aspects in the development of sustainable housing construction:

- contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and greenhouse gases (CO₂), which have a significant impact on climate change, while increasing the volume of construction of green housing. This, in turn, can be radically reduced through the introduction of energy-efficient technologies. Currently, total greenhouse gas emissions from the construction industry and building operations account for nearly 40% of global energy-related toxic gas emissions [4];

- traditional construction methods often result in unsustainable depletion of natural resources. In contrast, sustainable housing prioritizes recycled and local building materials and reduces the burden on limited resources;

- energy-efficient design features such as smart home technology, better insulation, and passive heating and cooling techniques help minimize energy consumption in green homes. This results in lower utility bills for homeowners and reduced burden on energy production systems;

- sustainable housing development prioritizes indoor air quality through the use of non-toxic building materials and the implementation of proper ventilation systems. This, in turn, ensures improved healthy living environments and the prevention of respiratory diseases.

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